

The Constitution of Marmelosin. Part I.

BY BRIJ BEHARI LAL DIKSHIT AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT.

In course of a previous investigation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 6, 759) the important medicinal plant *Aegle Marmelos* or the Indian Bel was thoroughly and completely examined from the root to the leaf by the present authors, who isolated from the fruit a colourless crystalline compound which they named "marmelosin" and which is most probably the active principle of the fruit. The present work is mainly devoted to the elucidation of the constitution of the substance.

Marmelosin is present in the fruit and in no other part of the plant. The percentage varies from 0.03 to 0.37 according to locality and cultivation, the small wild varieties of the fruit containing proportionately speaking much less of the material than the large cultivated variety. The drier the climate the smaller also is the yield of marmelosin. Fruits obtained from Bengal and Assam have often been found to contain more than five times as much marmelosin as those obtained from the U.P. and the Panjab, for the same weight of the fruit.

Marmelosin is a colourless crystalline substance with a faint smell reminding that of Bel. It crystallises in fine silky needles from petroleum ether and in large cubical crystals from alcohol. It is insoluble in water, but on boiling with water for a long time it melts to an oily liquid which on cooling again solidifies to somewhat greasy crystals, the substance being partially decomposed by the process. In ordinary saturated steam it is volatile only in traces, imparting to the condensed water its characteristic smell, but in superheated steam (200-210°) it readily volatilises with partial decomposition into anhydromarmelosin. When carefully heated by itself in a dry tube, it melts, partially carbonises, partly sublimes unchanged and is partly converted into the anhydride which condenses in the cooler parts of the tube. When quickly heated it decomposes completely with evolution of black fumes. Exposed to ordinary diffused sunlight marmelosin slowly assumes a yellow colour. In

strong direct sunlight marmelosin is converted into a sticky yellow resin in course of a week. Results of a series of analyses and determinations of the molecular weight by the cryoscopic, ebulliscent and lead salt methods point to a molecular formula $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$. One of the three oxygen atoms is in an alcoholic hydroxy group since marmelosin forms a monoacetyl, monobenzoyl and a monophenylurethane derivative, and also it dehydrates very easily with formation of anhydromarmelosin. It does not give any colour reaction or precipitate with neutral alcoholic ferric chloride, lead acetate or mercuric chloride.

Although marmelosin does not react with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine or semicarbazide, and does not reduce Fehling's solution yet it is found to reduce Tollen's reagent somewhat slowly. In its behaviour towards Tollen's reagent, it seems to resemble the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated lactones studied by Thiel (*Annalen*, 1901, 319, 155) and also more exhaustively by Jacobs and Hoffmann (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 67, 333). This view is confirmed by the fact that marmelosin develops an intense yellow colour with alcoholic caustic potash as in the case of the vast majority of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated lactones, and does not give any colour reaction with sodium nitroprusside. Thus all the three oxygen atoms of marmelosin are accounted for, one in an alcoholic hydroxy group and two in a lactonic grouping.

Marmelosin is unsaturated. It decolorises bromine water slowly and bromine in chloroform quite readily. By the action of bromine in alcohol or chloroform on marmelosin, a derivative was obtained containing three bromine atoms in the molecule. Volumetric estimation of unsaturation shows the presence of two double bonds in the compound and this anomalous position with regard to the above tribromo derivative can be explained by the assumption that in marmelosin the two unsaturated linkages are in a conjugated system. By the action of bromine, therefore, two atoms of the element are introduced at the extreme ends of the conjugated system and the third atom enters the molecule by substitution. The tetrabromo derivative of marmelosin which was obtained by the action of a large excess of bromine in carbon tetrachloride on marmelosin, could not be made to solidify.

Marmelosin readily adds on hydrogen by reduction with any strong acid reducing agents with formation of the dihydro derivative. The acetyl derivative of marmelosin could also be reduced and the product thus formed was found to be identical with the compound

obtained by simultaneous acetylation and reduction of marmelosin with zinc dust and acetic anhydride.

Marmelosin is optically active, having in alcohol a *dextro* rotation of $[\alpha]_{30}^0 = +36^\circ$. The optical activity and the *dextro* rotation was preserved in all the derivatives of marmelosin that have been prepared upto this time. The substance does not show any mutarotation.

Marmelosin is readily acted upon by concentrated hydrochloric acid, 75 per cent. sulphuric acid, anhydrous zinc chloride and phosphorus pentachloride and also by the action of heat, with elimination of a molecule of water and formation of anhydromarmelosin which is a colourless crystalline substance with a characteristic terpene like smell. In this formation the alcoholic hydroxy group is lost since anhydromarmelosin is no longer acted upon by acetylating or benzoylating agents. Anhydromarmelosin on account of its highly unsaturated nature soon undergoes transformation in the air and even in a sealed tube with formation of a sticky resinous substance.

By the action of fuming nitric acid on marmelosin, a mononitro derivative has been obtained crystallising in yellow needles. Fuming hydrobromic acid under pressure converts marmelosin into the monohydrobromide with simultaneous formation of large quantities of anhydromarmelosin. On fusion with caustic soda or potash, marmelosin adds on three molecules of water with formation of a compound $C_{13}H_{18}O_6$ which appears to be a hydroxy dibasic acid. A 3 per cent. alkaline solution of potassium permanganate readily acts upon marmelosin with formation of the same compound together with traces of succinic acid.

On distillation with zinc dust marmelosin is converted into anhydromarmelosin together with a number of its liquid and gaseous reduction and degradation products which could not be identified.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of marmelosin.—It has already been shown (Dikshit and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) that the most suitable solvent for the extraction of marmelosin from the dry Bel powder is petroleum ether, which also extracts the oil contained in the seeds of the fruit. The

proportion of marmelosin in the fruit differs within wide limits according to the locality and variety as the following table will show.

TABLE I.

Origin.	Marmelosin (%).
<i>Wild fruit collected from the jungles of eastern and southern</i>	
U.P. (mean of six samples)	0·07
Cultivated fruit from Allahabad (three samples)	0·25
Wild fruit from the Panjab	0·03
Cultivated fruit from the Panjab	0·13
(one sample each, Lahore and Delhi)	
Wild fruit from western U. P.	0·05
(four samples from Etawah)	
Cultivated fruit from Bengal	0·32 (Cal.)
(two samples, Calcutta and Dacca)	0·35 (Dac.)
Cultivated fruit from Assam	0·37
(one sample from Sylhet)	

To determine which particular portion of the fruit contained the largest proportion of marmelosin, a particular well-grown cultivated sample of the fruit collected locally was dissected and the various parts extracted with petroleum ether. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Part of the fruit.	Marmelosin (%).
Outer rind	Nil
Outer layer of pulp	0·15
Inner layer of pulp	0·46
Central core with the seeds and gum removed	0·08
Seeds	0·02
Gum	Nil

From the above it will appear that the greatest concentration of marmelosin is in the inner layer of the pulp, which is also incidentally the sweetest and most eaten by people and administered in disease.

For the extraction of marmelosin, the fully grown but unripe (ripe fruit is difficult to handle on account of its slow drying and fermenting propensities) cultivated fruits were broken to pieces, dried in the sun, ground to a fine powder in a mill and extracted with petroleum ether in a large Soxhlet's extraction apparatus.

From the extract, the solvent was distilled off until the volume was reduced to one-tenth of the original bulk and allowed to stand for a day when crude marmelosin crystallised out. This was filtered, washed with a little petroleum ether and pressed on porous plates until free from the adherent oil. It was then crystallised alternately from petroleum ether and alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal a number of times, until it was perfectly colourless and melted sharp at 103° .

Properties.—Marmelosin has a faint smell of Bel and a slight astringent taste. It is slightly soluble in benzene and petroleum ether, moderately soluble in alcohol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and pyridine and insoluble in water. It does not reduce Fehling's solution but ammoniacal silver nitrate is slowly reduced. It does not give any coloration or precipitate with ferric chloride, lead acetate, calcium chloride or silver nitrate, but on warming with basic lead acetate, a white precipitate of the lead salt is formed. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda solution (5%), but on heating it slowly dissolves with a brown colour. On acidification of the alkaline solution, a white precipitate of marmelosin comes down at once, and the mother liquor on standing slowly deposits another substance crystallising in brownish white needles melting at 146° and possessing the same molecular formula as marmelosin. On standing in contact with concentrated hydrochloric acid it is slowly reconverted into marmelosin. In all probability it is a compound with different type of lactonisation than marmelosin.

Marmelosin does not contain any methoxy or ethoxy group, as its treatment with the Zeissel's method of estimation of these groups gave negative results.

Physiologically marmelosin is an exceedingly potent drug and taken in doses of 0.05 g. it acts as a laxative and diuretic with a slight lowering of the respiration and a tendency towards sleepiness. In larger doses it acts as a strong depressant for the heart. A detailed physiological examination of the substance is in progress in the King George's Medical College, Lucknow. (Found: C, 72.47, 72.20, 72.02, 71.95; H, 5.64, 5.18, 5.46, 5.70; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 198, 202, 213; (ebulliscope in alcohol), 208, 212, 213; (lead salt), 216.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.5 per cent. M. W., 216).

Acetylmarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{11}O_2 \cdot O \cdot COCH_3$.—Marmelosin (1 g.) was treated with acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and fused zinc chloride

(2 g.) and the mixture heated under reflux for 15 minutes. On pouring into water a heavy oil separated which gradually solidified on long standing. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless silky needles melting at 214°. (Found: C, 69.51; H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.76; H, 5.4 per cent.).

Benzoylmarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{11}O_2 \cdot OC_6H_5$.—Marmelosin (1 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (30 c.c.) and benzoyl chloride (8 c.c.) gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and poured into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, when a voluminous white precipitate was obtained. This was filtered off and digested with dilute sodium carbonate solution in order to remove the benzoic acid formed and the residue crystallised from acetic acid with the addition of animal charcoal in pale brownish white needles, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: C, 74.71; H, 5.3. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent.).

Marmelosin-phenylurethane, $C_{13}H_{11}O_2 \cdot O \cdot NHCOC_6H_5$.—Marmelosin (1 g.) was treated with phenylisocyanate (5 c.c.) and the mixture warmed on the water-bath for 1 hour. On allowing the product to stand at the ordinary temperature for 1 day, the phenylurethane derivative crystallised out which was filtered off and washed with benzene until the smell of phenylisocyanate had completely disappeared. The substance was then recrystallised from alcohol in colourless silky needles, m.p. 245°. (Found: C, 71.41; H, 5.32. $C_{20}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 71.64; H, 5.07 per cent.).

Monobromomarmelosin dibromide, $C_{13}H_{11}O_3Br Br_2$.—Marmelosin (2 g.) dissolved in chloroform (120 c.c.) was treated with excess of bromine (4 c.c.) and the mixture allowed to stand for 4 hours in a dark place. It became quite warm and fumes of hydrogen bromide were given off. The solvent and the excess of bromine were then distilled off from a water-bath when a pasty semi-solid mass was obtained, which on standing over quick lime in a desiccator for nearly a month, solidified to a vitreous yellow mass. This on crystallisation from dilute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal gave pale yellow microscopic needles, m. p. 82°. (Found: Br, 52.4. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3Br_3$ requires Br, 52.6 per cent.).

The volumetric estimation of unsaturation in marmelosin was carried on as follows—marmelosin (0.3432 g.) was dissolved in carbon tetrachloride (10 c.c.) in a stoppered 250 c.c. measuring flask and $N/3$ -bromine (20 c.c.) in the same solvent added and the mixture allowed to stand in a dark place for 24 hours. The mixture was then

cooled in ice and water (25 c.c.) quickly added and well shaken and then 10 p.c. potassium iodide solution (25 c.c.) with water (75 c.c.) introduced and the whole thoroughly agitated. The iodine thus liberated was titrated against $N/10$ -sodium thio-sulphate. After titration, 2 p.c. potassium iodate (5 c.c.) was added and the titration repeated. Twice this value was deducted from the above titration value and the equivalents of bromine atoms taken up by the marmelosin molecule calculated, which came to 3.94. This means two double bonds in marmelosin.

Nitromarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{11}O_3 \cdot NO_2$.—Fuming nitric acid (30 c.c.) was cooled to 0° in a freezing mixture and marmelosin (2 g.) gradually added with thorough shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand at 0° for about 2 hours and then pieces of ice were added which caused the precipitation of a yellow flocculent substance. This was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow microscopic needles, m.p. 97° . (Found: N, 5.16. $C_{13}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent.).

Dihydromarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$.—Marmelosin (2 g.) was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) and the mixture treated with zinc dust (10 g.) in small quantities at a time. When the metal had nearly dissolved, the mixture was filtered hot into a large volume of cold water and the resultant white precipitate filtered off and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 238° . Unlike marmelosin this substance does not decolourise bromine water. (Found: C, 71.56; H, 6.62. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.41 per cent.).

Acetyldihydromarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{13}O_2 \cdot COCH_3$.—Marmelosin was simultaneously acetylated and reduced by heating the substance (2 g.) dissolved in hot acetic anhydride (50 c.c.) with slightly moist zinc dust (10 g.) and the acetyldihydro derivative isolated in a similar way to the above. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless microscopic needles, m.p. 176° . The substance is easily soluble in most of the organic solvents but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 69.5; H, 6.37. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.15 per cent.).

Marmelosin hydrobromide, $C_{13}H_{13}O_2 \cdot HBr$.—Marmelosin (2 g.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) was treated with fuming hydrobromic acid (10 c.c.) and the mixture heated under pressure in a tightly corked Florence flask immersed in a boiling water-bath. After 12 hours heating the flask was cooled and carefully opened and the contents poured into excess of cold water. The resultant

voluminous brown precipitate was filtered off and crystallised from dilute acetic acid with the addition of animal charcoal in brownish white microscopic needles, m.p. 156°. The mother liquor from the above on examination was found to contain comparatively large quantities of anhydromarmelosin. (Found: Br, 27.3. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3$ Br requires Br, 26.9 per cent.).

Anhydromarmelosin, $C_{13}H_{10}O_3$.—Finely powdered marmelosin (2 g.) was treated with sulphuric acid (75 p.c., 50 c.c.) and the mixture heated on the water-bath under reflux for 12 hours. On dilution with water a light brown oil separated out which was thoroughly washed with water by decantation and then extracted with ether. After drying with anhydrous calcium chloride the ether was removed by distillation and the residual viscous oil allowed to stand in the vacuum desiccator for a week, when it solidified to a crystalline mass. This was recrystallised from petroleum ether with the addition of animal charcoal in colourless silky needles, m.p. 76°, and possessing a penetrating terpene like odour. The substance is easily soluble in most of the organic solvents, but insoluble in water. Unlike marmelosin it is readily volatile in steam and can also be purified in this way. (Found: C, 78.92; H, 5.8. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 78.78; H, 5.5 per cent.).

Action of heat on marmelosin.—Marmelosin (2 g.) was heated in a small conical flask fitted with an air condenser and suspended in an air-bath. The temperature of the latter was raised at the rate of one degree per minute. Marmelosin at first melted to a colourless liquid which gradually passed through various shades of yellow and brown to almost black and evolved vapours which condensed on the sides of the condenser in the form of glistening crystals. The latter which melted at 76° was identified to be anhydromarmelosin, while from the black carbonaceous residue a further quantity was recovered by steam distillation. The residue left after this, on extraction with alcohol, yielded small quantities of unchanged marmelosin.

Action of phosphorus pentachloride on marmelosin.—Phosphorus pentachloride readily acted upon marmelosin either in the solid state or in benzene solution with formation of anhydromarmelosin. No chloro derivative of marmelosin could be isolated from the reaction mixture.

Fusion of marmelosin with caustic potash.—Marmelosin (5 g.), solid caustic potash (30 g.) and water (10 c.c.) were fused together

in a nickel crucible and the melt maintained at 140-50° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On cooling it was dissolved in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. A brown precipitate was obtained which was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 245°. The substance appears to be an aliphatic acid. (Found: C, 57.33; H, 6.71%). Taking it to be dibasic the molecular weight by the lead salt and the silver salt comes to 267.3 and 269.2 respectively. From these data the formula $C_{13}H_{18}O_6$ appears likely.

The aqueous mother liquor from the above precipitate on extraction with large quantities of ether and subsequent evaporation of the solvent yielded another substance crystallising from small quantity of water in colourless prisms, m.p. 98° and which was identified to be oxalic acid.

Oxidation of marmelosin with potassium permanganate.—Marmelosin (5 g.) in dilute caustic soda solution was treated with a 3 p.c. aqueous solution of potassium permanganate at the ordinary temperature until the latter was no longer decolourised. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off and from the filtrate on acidification, the same acid melting at 245°, as described above, was isolated in a similar manner. The mother liquor was found to contain traces of succinic acid.

Zinc dust distillation of marmelosin.—Marmelosin (5 g.) on distillation with zinc dust in the usual manner yielded a viscid yellow oil smelling strongly of anhydromarmelosin, and from which the latter was recovered in minute quantities by steam distillation. The greater part of the oil did not solidify, nor could it be purified to yield any constant analytical data. Qualitative tests indicated it to be a mixture of hydrocarbons. During the distillation gaseous products were also evolved which did not condense even in a freezing mixture, and consisted mostly of aliphatic hydrocarbons as they burnt on ignition with a luminous non-sooty flame. No other important product could be isolated.

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